

CONSOLIDATION OF BRAID-BASED CFRP STRUCTURES USING AN EXPANDABLE MANDREL

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1 Introduction

One of the most interesting preform technologies especially for longish geometries is the braiding technique. In combination with hollow and removable cores this technique can be one of the most effective for carbon fiber reinforced structures in high volume production. Among the composite applications it competes with filament winding, pultrusion and tape lay-up methods [1]. These different methods are all interesting for longitudinal and hollow structures but limited by their manufacturing technology itself regarding geometry and textile structure. The braiding technology is used to manufacture near-net shaped preforms using a robot which guides the mandrel through the center of a braiding machine for overbraiding. Beside advantages like automation and high volume production, a third yarn system (0°-yarn) can be implemented during the braiding process. In this way longitudinal parts can be reinforced with biaxially-oriented (torsional load) and triaxially-oriented yarns (flexural load).

In combination with a mandrel which is suitable for the whole process chain (Braiding, Infusion, Curing, Demoulding) it becomes very interesting for high volume production. In order to implement a manufacturing process which fulfills requirements for high volume production, Bernet [2] shows that using an expandable mandrel in combination with braiding technology offers a good possibility for high volume production. An inflatable bladder offers the possibility to consolidate the impregnated preform during curing. At the end of the process the mandrel can be removed by simply deflating the bladder by removing the pressure.

The structure of a braid shows disadvantages regarding mechanical performance in comparison to e.g. wound structures. Braided sleeves are built up by the intertwining of yarns which leads to out-of-plane waviness due to the yarns crossing each other.

Previous studies [3], [4] describe that CFRP structures which are based on braids or weaves show lower performance in stiffness and strength compared to structures based on non-crimped fabrics (NCF).

The advantage of using an inflatable mandrel in order to reduce time and costs for the production of hollow braided parts is shown and already used in different applications, for example tennis rackets or bicycle parts.

Lehmann [5] describes the draping behaviour of biaxial braided sleeves. This behaviour explains the possibility of enlarging the impregnated preform during curing and the simplified demoulding after the curing process. This studies are focused on biaxial structures and does not consider triaxial structures.

First investigations [6] show how an inflatable bladder affects the laminate structure in comparison to a CFRP structure which is manufactured on a steel mandrel. Shafts are manufactured and analysed based on laminate quality and torsional performance. All are manufactured with 3 layers of braid. To gain first experience the inflatable bladder is pressurized with 4bar during the curing process. The enlargement caused by the bladder ranges from 25.1mm to 26mm. A shaft with an inner diameter of 26mm is manufactured using a steel mandrel for comparison. The effect on the structure is visible regarding fiber volume fraction (FVF), wall thickness and reduced undulation. Micrographs show the path of the braiding rovings in which the effect of consolidation is presented.

Comparing torsional stiffness, the pressurized version presents a slightly improved performance. However the FVF is different, which affects the wall thickness. The improvement cannot be explained by yarn consolidation.

Another point has to be considered regarding this study [6]. The pressurized version is braided over a mandrel with smaller outer diameter which is then

enlarged by inflating the bladder. For comparison, a steel mandrel is used to manufacture a preform which is directly braided on a dimension required for the cured part. The larger diameter of the mandrel leads to a lower crimp on which the braiding yarns have to be positioned.

Besides the difference regarding manufacturing costs, it is presented that there is no disadvantage for the laminate structure. This study gives a first idea about biaxial braid behaviour.

The Study presented in this work is focused on the question if using an inflatable bladder gives the possibility of affecting the laminate quality after the braiding process in a positive manner. It does not only consider the changes of FVF but rather the influence on the textile structure.

The main intention is to gain knowledge about the relation between diameter and type of mandrel, textile structure and pressure level during curing. Particularly investigated is the behaviour of specimens based on a triaxial structure.

Therefore, the paper is focused on laminate characterisation of manufactured tubes and does not consider mechanical properties.

Another intention for this type of analysis is the demand for prediction of the mechanical behaviour of braid-based CFRP-structures. Due to the braiding process and the effects caused by various process parameters, the structural behaviour is complex and makes it complicated to predict the mechanical behaviour.

An accurate geometric modelling of braids is essential for accurately defining and predicting the mechanical properties of the structure. [1] Alpyldiz [1] proposes a simple 3D geometrical model for the yarn paths composing of tubular braids, which takes the crimp of the braiding yarn into account.

In the beginning of his work he describes different models found in literature. But most of them describe 2D models or do not consider the tubular braid or the undulation of the braiding yarn caused by the crimp. The model proposed by Alpyldiz has been applied for one layer of braid for regular, diamond tubular braids, and also for the triaxial diamond tubular braid. The latter are interesting for this work as the used textile structure given by the braiding machine and the amount of braiding yarns is based on biaxial and triaxial diamond braid.

The geometrical model is compared with the shape and geometry of the rovings in the manufactured specimens. Micrographs in braiding roving direction present how the rovings are shaped in a cured part.

2 The Braiding Technique

During the braiding process, the bobbins move on the inner side of the braiding machine (Fig. 1) crossing sinusoidal paths. By using a pair of bobbins where each is running in the opposite direction, the yarns are crossing each other in a repeating manner. In that way a braided sleeve is manufactured in the middle of the braiding machine.

The mandrel is guided by a robot through the center of the braiding machine for overbraiding.

Fig. 1 Herzog Radial Braider, 64 Carriers

A third yarn direction (0° -yarns) can be incorporated in between of two crossing braiding yarns. (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2: Braiding of a sleeve consisting of a triaxial braid

Fig. 3 shows how the braiding yarns (bias yarns), and in Fig. 4 a full amount of 0° -yarns are positioned on a mandrel after overbraiding. The drawing shows the structure and the position of the yarns on a mandrel with round cross section.

Fig. 3: Biaxial Braid [7]

Fig. 4: Triaxial Braid [7]

Depending on the application requirements and expected loads the most parts are designed with more than one layer of braid. In the pre-dimensioning process of a part, the amount of layers is defined. Therefore, a preform can be manufactured with several amounts of layers which are braided on top of each other.

3 Undulation in out-of-plane Direction

Alongside parameters like yarn geometry, amount of yarns and layers, waviness is an essential parameter which affects the mechanical performance regarding textile structure. Waviness is described by the undulation in out-of-plane direction which is caused by the crossing points of the braiding yarns.

In the work of Birkefeld [7] a unit cell of a biaxial and triaxial braid is visualized as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. In the triaxial braid (Fig. 6) the undulations of braiding yarns are increased by the 0°-yarns. The incorporated 0°-yarns are undulating inbetween the crossing points as well.

Fig. 5: Principle of a biaxial braid (unit cell) [7]

Fig. 6: Principle of a triaxial braid (unit cell) [7]

In literature, it is difficult to find a clear and suitable definition of the undulation of the braiding yarn. One definition which describes the crimp of a yarn in a weave is given by Cherif [4]. It is described with the incorporated yarn length in relation to the original, elongated length. The disadvantage for the manufacturing process is that the yarn has to be pulled out for measurement. This kind of measurement is not practicable for a manufacturing process of CFRP structures. Therefore a method which can predict the undulation by using parameters like yarn width and layer thickness, without destroying the preform is interesting. In Fig. 7 the parameters for the description of the sinusoidal undulation used by Alpyldiz [1] is shown.

Fig. 7: Crimp path of the braiding yarn revolving in the counter-clockwise direction for diamond braid structure [1]

The geometrical model is interesting and practicable for one layer of braid. In comparison to other definitions found in literature, Alpyldiz describes the path of a tubular braid, considering 3D coordinates and the undulation. Though as well as other geometrical models they act on the assumption that the fibers lay nearly perfect elliptical or lenticular shaped.

Comparing the micrographs of CRFP specimens, like Birkefeld [7], it is visible that the geometrical model describes the shape in a perfect way. Comparing the geometrical models with measurements of micrographs it is visible that the shape of the rovings is varying and not always regularly distributed. Those effects can influence the yarn path of the crossing yarn.

An ideal position, as described in the model of Alpyldiz is not given if you compare the geometrical model with a micrograph of a CFRP structure with 3 layers of biaxial braid (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Comparison between a) yarn path described by Alpyldiz and b) micrograph in braiding yarn direction of a CFRP structure based on 3 layers of biaxial braid

Manufacturing parameters like yarn tension, type of roving, diameter of mandrel (wrapping angle), type of weave (amount of crossing points) and the amount of layers have effect on the lay-up. The shape of the roving cross section is influenced by those braiding parameters and type of infusion, especially the consolidation pressure.

4 Draping Behavior of Biaxial Braided Sleeves

Previous studies [6] as well as the work of Lehmann [8] describe the drapability of a biaxial braided sleeve. In his work Lehman [5] describes that a diameter change of a biaxial braided tube can be mathematically explained as follows:

$$l_2 = \frac{l_1 \sqrt{\left(\frac{D_1}{D_2}\right)^2 - \sin^2 \alpha_1}}{\cos \alpha_1} \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha_2 = \arcsin\left(\frac{D_2}{D_1} \times \sin \alpha_1\right) \quad (2)$$

As presented in Fig. 9 it is possible to change the diameter of the sleeve by pulling in length direction, thus decreasing the diameter. The other way around it is possible to enlarge the diameter by shortening the length.

Fig. 9: Coherence of diameter and fiber angle of braided tubes [1]

By the possibility to enlarge the diameter of the braided sleeve as described in [6], it is possible to remove the bladder after the curing process [6].

In the investigation work of Lehmann and Michaeli focused on improvements of a resin transfer molding process with an inflatable bladder parameters like internal bladder pressure, RTM pressure, and movement of the braid in the cavity are investigated. Lehman's investigation shows that the braid can only move in areas with larger diameter if it is possible to shorten the tube in length as well [8].

5 Coherence between Expansion of Bladder and Effect on the Yarn Path

The path of a yarn on a tubular mandrel can be described as shown in Fig. 10.

The braiding yarns follow a helical path with a constant helix angle, which is the braid angle with the horizontal axes, over the cylindrical mandrel. [1]

Fig. 10: The path of the braiding yarns (one from the set of braiding yarns moving in the counter-clockwise direction and one from the set of braiding yarns moving in the clockwise direction) on the cylindrical mandrel (a) set of axes on perspective view, (b) side view. [1]

For investigating the path of one yarn a view in the direction of one braiding yarn is necessary. This means a cut in direction of 45° (braiding angle) to the longitudinal axis (Z-direction) of the tube. To visualize and explain the assumption that the undulation in a braiding yarn can be reduced Fig. 11 shows a drawing in which the effect of an inflated bladder on the yarn path in radial direction is shown.

Fig. 11: a) braiding yarn path in a dry preform, braided on an inflatable bladder b) yarn path after impregnation and consolidation, pressurizing the inflatable bladder c) comparison of consolidated and non-consolidated yarn by an inflatable bladder

The idea is to use the pressure in the bladder to elongate and consolidate several yarns in the braid. At the point where the length cannot be shortened, there is no possibility for inter-fiber shearing and diameter change. It is assumed that at this point the undulations which are described before and showed in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 can be reduced. There are two

main steps happening. Pressurizing the bladder leads to an expansion in radial direction. This leads to an enlargement of preform diameter by shortening the length at the same time (Fig. 9). The moment where the enlargement of diameter and shortening in length direction are stopped, the yarns are elongated and consolidated. (Fig. 11)

All these explanations are simplified as they consider only one layer of braid considered. The most applications for components based on CFRP structures consist of more than one layer preform and a third yarn direction.

This means that the layers are braided with a specific tension one over another. The interaction regarding diameter change during pressurizing the bladder in between the layers raises the question if the described change of yarn path (Fig. 11) can be caused in the second and third layer as well.

Alpyldiz describes the yarn path in form of a sine function. [1] Considering that a change of the amplitude is expected it has to be explained that this can only be reached if it is possible to transmit pressure from the bladder to the first layer, from the first layer to the second layer and from the second layer to the third layer. Therefore the movement from the lower layer has to be large enough to cause an effect in the upper layer.

In the same way the diameter change of a braid stays in relation to the change of the length.

A third yarn direction changes the behavior of the braid. The 0°- yarns which are interwoven in between the crossing points cause additional undulations and have an influence on the enlargement caused by the bladder.

5 Manufacturing of Specimens

The target is to manufacture specimens with a simple geometry which can show the effects of the process and the bladder. Therefore tubes are manufactured with the geometries described in Table 1.

Inner Diameter [mm]	25.1 – 25.9
Outer Diameter [mm]	30.2 – 31.6
Tube Length [mm]	600 mm

Table 1: Specimen geometry

The inner and outer diameter of the specimen depend on the way in which they are manufactured and if they are based on a biaxial or a triaxial braid.

5.1 Preform and Infiltration Process

The preforms are manufactured with carbon rovings of type Tenax HTS 40 F13 12k. One version of specimens is manufactured with 3 layers of biaxial braid and the other one with 3 layers of triaxial braid.

As the focus of this work lies on the behavior of the braid the infiltration process is done without a mold on the outer site. The preforms are infiltrated in the same way as described in [1]. A vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) with production parameters that are common for those types of preforms is used. The vacuum bag is expandable enough to realize that the braid can expand as much as possible. The specimens are manufactured with the epoxy – based resin Momentive EPIKOTE™ Resin MGS® RIMR 235/RIMH236.

The Fiber Volume Fraction (FVF) of CFRP's that are manufactured by VARI is regulated by the vacuum level during curing. By pressurizing the expandable tube the FVF can be increased and regulated in a similar manner to the curing process in an autoclave. [6].

5.2 The Mandrel

The draping behavior of a biaxial braid, the diameter of the mandrel and the textile structure in combination with an inflatable bladder, has an influence on the quality of a cured part. Therefore, different types of mandrel are necessary for specimen manufacturing.

Table 2 shows an overview of used mandrels. Each of them has a specific task and reason for the use in this test series. The mandrel which is used for consolidation is combined with an inherent stable material (aluminum mandrel) and an expandable tube (inflatable bladder). Using this combination it is possible to overbraid the inherent stable mandrel.

Manufactured Sample	Type of Mandrel	Outer Diameter (Mandrel) [mm]	Geometry Description (Mandrel)	Special Process Parameter (During Curing)
NP_25.1	Aluminum+ Bladder Material	25.1	round cross section	no pressurizing
B_MO	Aluminum+ Bladder Material	25.1	round cross section,, Movement in Length direction possible	bladder is pressurized with the pressure level of 4 and 6 bar
B_BL	Aluminum+ Bladder Material	25.1	round cross section with \varnothing -change at both ends Movement in length direction BLocked	bladder is pressurized with the pressure level of 4 and 6 bar
NP_25.9	Steel	25.9	round cross section	no pressurizing

Table 2: Types of mandrel

The samples “NP-25.1” are manufactured with the intention to see how fibers and braid are structured in the laminate without pressurizing the bladder.

Samples “6B-MO” are manufactured to investigate how the pressurized bladder affects the preform when it has the possibility to shorten in length direction.

Samples “6B-BL” are manufactured on a mandrel that has specific diameter changes at both ends of the longitudinal mandrel. (Fig. 12) That way the movement of the braid in longitudinal direction is blocked.

Fig. 12: Detail of mandrel type “B_BL”

The samples “NP_25.9” are manufactured on a steel mandrel with no additional bladder and no possibility to pressurize from the inner side during curing. The intention is to manufacture samples in which the yarns are directly positioned on a larger diameter during the braiding process. The warping of a mandrel with a higher diameter leads to another yarn lay-up.

The second intention is to compare the yarn path with samples “6B-BL” and “6B-MO”. A comparison should clarify if there is a difference between manufacturing a preform directly on a diameter which is required for the final part or a smaller diameter which can be enlarged with a bladder towards the required geometry during the curing process.

All mandrels were used for specimens based on biaxial preform (“sample_BIAX”) and triaxial preform (“sample_TRIAX”).

7 Evaluation of Results

7.1 Specimen geometry

Measurements such as inner and outer diameter of specimens are determined with a caliper. Due to the fact that the specimens are manufactured with a VARI process the outer surface is rippled. This means that the determined values describe the

maximum. Wall thickness is calculated from values of measured inner and outer diameter.

7.2 Consolidation

The evaluation of specimens is done by photomicrographs. Micrographs are cut from cured parts in direction of the braiding yarn (45° to the longitudinal axis of the tube).

As only the outer layer is visible the cut is done along the roving on the outer layer. In that way it is possible to visualize one braiding yarn path in each layer. However, the cutting position, regarding the roving cross section, cannot be defined because the layers are not placed perfectly over each other. The shape of the roving is elliptical or lenticular and the cutting position shows a different thickness of the roving. Fig. 13 presents a cut through two rovings in two layers of braid.

Fig. 13: Drawing of a cut through two rovings which lay over each other

It is not possible to measure the height of the yarns and to compare values directly. Therefore, focus is put on the consolidation effect. As described in literature a yarn path can be described by a sine wave. The geometry of the roving has an influence on the amplitude and the length of the sine wave. Consolidation should mean that the amplitude of the sine wave is decreasing whereas the wave length is increasing. A more uniform yarn path is expected as well.

Fig. 14: BI_NP_26 [6]

Therefore, the specimens are evaluated by measuring the height [h] of the yarn at ten different positions along one yarn path (sine wave) Fig. 14. The experimental standard deviation [s] of those values is taken into account for the evaluation.

In the following, specimens are described with the sample number which is defined by the preform structure (BI = biax), the pressure level (4 = 4bar) and the type of mandrel which is used.

7.3 Biaxial Braid

7.3.1 Geometry and FVF

Table 3 shows the results which are gained from measuring the specimens and chemical analysis for determining FVF.

Specimen “BI_6B_BL” shows that a higher pressure level causes a small difference in diameter change and 2 % increase of FVF.

It has to be considered that the change of diameter and wall thickness can be caused by the reduced amount of resin and flattening of the yarns. Micrographs cut in direction of the braiding yarn should give some insight about the influence on consolidation of laminate and yarn path.

	Inner-ø [mm]	Outer-ø [mm]	Wall Thickness [mm]	FVF [%]
BI_NP_25.1	25,1	30,19	2,54	56
BI_4B_MO	26,05	30,82	2,39	59
BI_4B_BL	25,59	30,33	2,37	58,6
BI_6B_BL	25,63	30,41	2,39	60,3
BI_NP_25.9	25,9	30,1	2,55	57,4

Table 3: Measurement data (biaxial specimens)

Due to the fact that the specimens are manufactured using the VARI process, consolidation pressure and level is limited by the vacuum. Using an inflatable bladder the FVF can be significantly increased.

Especially the specimen cured with the higher pressure level of 6 bar shows an increase of nearly 3-4 %.

In the same way the results show that the diameter is enlarging up to 26 mm if the possibility for shortening in length direction is given.

Comparing the specimens “BI_4B_MO” and “BI_4B_BL” the FVF is the nearly same whereas the enlargement of the diameter is less (BI_4B_BL). These results verify that the diameter change depends on the shortening in length direction as described by Lehmann.

7.3.2 The Consolidation

Fig. 15, Fig. 16, Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 show the micrographs of the biaxial specimens with a view along the braiding yarn path. Those are used for the evaluation of the consolidation effect.

The path of one yarn direction and the cross section of the crossing yarns are visible.

The arithmetic mean [\bar{h}] and the experimental standard deviation [s] are derived from measured values (Table 4).

Fig. 15: BI_NP_25.1

Fig. 17: BI_4B_BL

Fig. 16: BI_4B_MO [6]

Fig. 18: BI_6B_MO

The smaller the value for standard deviation the less is the dispersion of measured height values. Results measured in the first layers of specimens show that the bladder and higher diameter of mandrel affect uniformity of the yarn path. Specimen “BI_NP_25.1” presents the highest result of dispersion in all layers.

Values presented for the second and third layer present a smaller dispersion for specimens which were pressurized. In comparison to the first layer, values of the second and third layer present higher standard deviation for all specimens.

		BI_NP_25.1	BI_4B_MO	BI_4B_BL	BI_6B_BL	BI_NP_25.9
1st Layer	\bar{h} [mm]	0,32	0,40	0,33	0,31	0,30
	s	0,05	0,03	0,03	0,03	0,03
2nd Layer	\bar{h} [mm]	0,43	0,35	0,29	0,40	0,37
	s	0,06	0,05	0,04	0,05	0,06
3rd Layer	\bar{h} [mm]	0,43	0,39	0,29	0,40	0,41
	s	0,06	0,04	0,04	0,05	0,05

Table 4: Measurements of yarn path (biaxial specimens)

7.4 Triaxial Braid

Results gained by the biaxial preforms show the difference of using 4 bar and 6 bar pressure level during curing. The best result regarding FVF and consolidation can be reached with 6 bar (Table 3). Therefore, the pressurized version of triaxial specimens (TR) is just cured with 6 bar and there are no specimens manufactured with the pressure level of 4 bar.

7.4.1 Geometry and FVF

	Inner- ϕ [mm]	Outer- ϕ [mm]	Wall Thickness [mm]	FVF [%]
TR_NP_25,1	25,1	31,18	3,03	56,6
TR_6B_MO	25,88	31,52	2,82	63,7
TR_6B_BL	25,83	31,59	2,88	63,6
TR_NP_25,9	25,95	31,62	2,84	56,4

Table 5 Measurement data (triaxial braid)

Results gained are presented in Table 5. Similar to biaxial specimens it is visible that the use of inflatable bladder during curing leads to a higher FVF. It is assumed that the FVF is higher in comparison to the biaxial specimens as there are more rovings (0°-yarns) incorporated in the braid.

The comparison of the specimen “TR_NP_25.1” and “TR_6B_MO” shows that pressurizing the bladder leads to a higher enlargement of diameter but not as much as if a biaxial structure is pressurized. This leads to the assumption that the draping behavior, as described by Lehmann for biaxial braids [8], is influenced by the incorporated 0°-yarns.

Comparing the specimens of triaxial structure, “TR_6B_BL” and biaxial structure “BI_6B_BL”, it is presented that the enlargement of the triaxial structure is larger. It is assumed that the higher enlargement is only caused by the flattening of the 0°-yarns.

The specimens TR_6B_MO are compared with TR_6B_BL. The enlargement of the inner diameter is more or less the same. The difference is minimal.

This effect verifies the assumption that the enlargement of diameter is not caused by shortening the length but rather by flattening the 0°-yarns.

7.4.2 Consolidation

Fig. 19, Fig. 20, Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 present the micrographs. Due to 0°-yarns, the yarn path shows higher amplitude in comparison to the yarn path of the of the biaxial specimen.

Results of the measurements, which are done in the same way as for the biaxial specimens, are presented in Table 6.

Conspicuous are the results of specimen “TR_NP_25.1” where the results in all layers present the same standard deviation. The specimens “TR_6B_MO” and “TR_6B_BL” present a lower dispersion of values in the first layer in comparison to the second and third one.

Especially specimen “TR_6B_BL” shows a less uniform yarn path in the third layer.

Fig. 19 : TR_NP_25.1

Fig. 21: TR_6B_BL

Fig. 20: TR_6B_MO

Fig. 22: TR_NP_26

		TR_NP_25.1	TR_6B_MO	TR_6B_BL	TR_NP_25.9
1st Layer	\bar{h} [mm]	0,32	0,40	0,40	0,39
	s	0,05	0,04	0,02	0,09
2nd Layer	\bar{h} [mm]	0,43	0,41	0,39	0,40
	s	0,05	0,05	0,04	0,06
3rd Layer	\bar{h} [mm]	0,38	0,31	0,41	0,40
	s	0,05	0,05	0,08	0,05

Table 6: Measurement data of yarn path (triaxial specimen)

8. Conclusion and Outlook

Measurements of the tube and analysis of micrograph give an idea about the behavior and effects of an inflatable bladder on the structure in the laminate. The results show that the behavior is combined by the change of FVF, consolidation of yarns and draping behavior of the textile structure.

The effect on the FVF by using an inflatable bladder is verified for 4 and 6 bar pressure level. By using different types of mandrel the description of Lehman for the behavior of biaxial braided sleeves is verified. Diameter enlargement is depending on the shortening of the preform in length direction.

The same behavior cannot be shown for the specimens based on triaxial structures. The 0°-yarns influence the draping behavior. There is no visible difference in the diameter change when comparing specimens where the preform can shorten in length direction with those where the shortening is not possible. It is assumed that the enlargement of diameter for the triaxial specimens can be explained by the consolidation of the 0°-yarns in the crossing points.

The exact influence on the consolidation of the 0°-yarns is not considered, but will be done in future work.

The evaluation of micrographs presents that yarn measurements cannot be measured and compared directly. Therefore, the uniformity of yarn paths is measured. The interpretation of results gives an idea about how the uniformity of the yarn path is affected by the bladder. Especially the first layer of all pressurized versions (biaxial and triaxial) is consolidated by the bladder. Only the results of the biaxial specimens (BI_6B_BL, BI_4B_BL, BI_4B_MO) present an influence on the second and third layer.

It can be said that the shape and path of the bias yarn which are consolidated by the bladder look more like the geometrical model presented by Alpyldiz.

Further studies are planned in which the effect on mechanical properties is investigated. By using an outer mold and knowledge gained until now, specimens based on biaxial and triaxial braids will be manufactured. Further work is planned to clarify the question of how the effects described in this work affect the mechanical performance.

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